

INGILIZ TILINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TEXNOLOGIYANING RO‘LI VA DARSNI SODDALASHTIRISH

Sobirova Mavjuda Solijon qizi

Toshkent davlat pedagogika universitetining talabasi

E-mail: mavjudasobirova56@gmail.com

ANNOTASIYA

Mazkur maqolada ingliz tilini o‘qitishda va rivojlantirishda texnologiyaning ro‘li va ahamiyati haqida so‘z yuritiladi. Xususan, dars paytida bolalarning diqqatini tortish uchun qiziqarli yo‘llar orqali texnikadan unumli foydalanish. Ularning aqliy holatini fanga jalb qilish uchun har tomonlama qo‘llab, mavzuni yoritish uchun texnologiyani dars paytida faol foydalanish haqida bayon etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: multimedia vositalari, harakatli strategiya, aqliy hujum, o‘yinlar makoni, nutq faolligi.

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY TO DEVELOP ENGLISH AND SIMPLIFYING THE LESSON FOR LEARNERS

ABSTRACT

This article discusses The importance of technology while teaching and developing english in the lesson. In particular, we can use technology devices in order to attract pupils’ interests while teaching or learning english. It involves all cases of technique actively bot order to organize The simplest lesson in accordance with their mental positions and their general situations ,by The way affect to sit calmly in The lesson and not feel tired while learning something or doing warm-up activities.

Keywords: The devices of multimedia, strategic ways, The attack for brain, The cite for games, The active of speech.

Firstly, technology is not a new term in our today’s world. In all subjects, we can use freely from The technique, since it demands to develop The level of The lesson from all aspects of activities, As an example, for our theoretical purpose or our practical views based on a certain topic. It can aid by devices in The following ways:

- mass media (scientific Journals for adults)
- picture book
- online TV
- tablets and so on

Technology has become an integral part of sustaining society, and its influence on education is inevitable. Earlier, technology's role in education was limited to teaching methodologies and educating students. The evolution of technology has impacted every aspect of our lives, from banking to how we communicate. Education is inextricably linked to technology, so its integration into technology is inevitable. As a result, it is not surprising that schools have also become a part of this paradigm shift in the world today. Technology has been part of our lives for decades, but it is only recently that the development and application of technology in education have begun to take shape. Technology is one of the most important things we have today, which can assist students in doing better academically. As technology grows, it brings about new ways for students to learn and interact through various mediums.

Learners gain more Advantages by using technology. For instance, they can save their time by watching online videos, shows, cartoons, films. They learn new words in a context to improve Speaking and listening skills which are first positions to learn English, besides they watch those characteristics of The film and attitude to that. They may broaden their outlook in a line with The help of The technology. [Alasaf, H. A. (2014). Effective strategies on using ICT for teaching and learning undergraduate level at Jordanian universities. *Journal of Education and Practice*,5(3), 81–89p]

My method is CLT during The process of The lesson, since The learners debate each other, ask interactive questions to take extraordinary answers.

We know, technology is not a simple way, this term consists of nine letters that, they should find out new words from every letters from toy on online TV to separate into two groups, furthermore The next person should Explain that word to The next person to prepare into The lesson.

This is an Introduction part for pupils, Then Teachers should be active to give illustrations. One of the techniques in using video as teaching media is applying video annotations. Video annotations is a technique of video presentation which includes "clipping," or the selection and naming of specific segments of video from longer videos in order to emphasize parts of videos which is important (Bossewitch & Preston, 2011). According to the dual-coding theory by Paivio (1971):

"when pictures are added to the meaning, the number of signals connected with the message increases. Viewers then will be more probable to keep the message in mind."

That is the reason why annotations are necessary to give the students complete aspects of the language; the picture, the sound, the words, and the context when the language is used. With the aim of creating an effective learning process with a limited time, the use of video annotations will be the best choice.

To sum up, the use of video as teaching media in English teaching is very useful. In order to find how the students' respond to video with annotations which is implemented in English classroom, this study will be focused on using video with annotations in teaching English expression. The study is a good chance to hold in a class of XI grade students .[<https://edubirdie.com/examples/technology-in-language-learning/>]

CONCLUSION

In my personal view, technology strategies affect to develop english As a central role, As it gives a specific outcome and achievement in a line . This a stage for one by one also new learners. YOU TUBE is a ready online Tutor for learners to simplify The topic with The clear Examples.

Technology that is made use of in the classroom is very beneficial in helping the students understand and absorb what they are being taught. For instance, since there are a number of students who are visual learners, projection screens connected to computers could be put in classrooms to let the students see their notes as opposed to simply sitting down and listening to the instructor teach.

There is a number of very good software that can be used to supplement the class curriculum. The programs make available to students quizzes, tests, activities and study questions that could help the students continue with the learning process when they are out of the classroom.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Alassaf, H. A. (2014). Effective strategies on using ICT for teaching and learning undergraduate level at Jordanian universities. *Journal of Education and Practice*,5(3), 81–89p
- 2) Ali, J. K. M. (2017). Blackboard as a motivator for Saudi EFL students: A psycholinguistic study. *International Journal of English Linguistics*,144–151 p
- 3) <https://edubirdie.com/examples/technology-in-language-learning/>
- 4) https://www.academia.edu/11266866/Essay_The_Importance_of_Learning_English